

Flexibility and precision: Manufacturing concept for folded tessellated lightweight carbon-reinforced concrete slabs

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Abstract

The integration of the high strength, low weight, and corrosion resistance properties of carbon-reinforced concrete (CRC) with the symmetry, compatibility, and flexibility inherent in origami waterbomb pattern geometries facilitates the design of thin-walled, highly efficient CRC modular shells. These modular shells can be assembled into extensive and complex structural systems. However, assembling a large number of folded modules necessitates stringent geometric tolerances in the CRC modules to ensure geometric compatibility. Achieving high precision in the production of CRC modular shell components to maintain their geometric integrity remains a significant challenge. This study aims to present an advanced manufacturing methodology employing a pneumatic folding tool with non-orthogonal facets. This innovative and sustainable approach enables automated, precise, and productive sharp-edged folding of fresh carbon-reinforced concrete. To achieve this, various folding mechanisms are explored to identify the optimal folding configuration that accounts for the high geometric dependency due to the coupled degrees of freedom along the folding lines and the manufacturing precision. A series of 3D scan measurements is conducted to pinpoint operational weaknesses within the selected folding mechanism. This analysis assesses the joint fidelity of the folding lines, identifies limitations, and evaluates the geometrical flexibility of the optimal folding mechanisms. Finally, it is demonstrated that a folding kinematic concept which accommodates flexible non-orthogonal discretization of a faceted tool surface – combined with a multi-degree-of-freedom actuation system – enables productive folding of fresh textile-reinforced concrete sheets into complex customizable geometries.

1 Introduction

The advancements of CRC provide promising structural capabilities of such material-minimized, thin-walled constructions [1-3]. The synergy of carbon-reinforcement and concrete allows the design of lightweight, high-efficient and environment-friendly folded structures. However, traditional methods for casting such structures have proven labor-intensive and ineffective [4]. Usage of textile fabrics as reinforcement in cementitious composites like carbon-reinforced concrete (CRC) opens up new design options for thin-walled structural elements. Textile's foldability can be exploited to achieve structurally efficient design by exploiting the kinematics of rigid folding, a subclass of origami shaping principles.

This paper reports on recent development along this design principle, presenting a manufacturing approach to modular structural elements by folding reinforced layers of concrete in fresh state [5]. The modules are folded using a novel pneumatic folding tool [6] exploiting the rigid folding kinematics of the waterbomb base [7, 8]. The periodicity of the waterbomb tessellation is exploited to introduce compatible, interlockable module geometry.

A crucial question included in this development is the precision of the folding process on the one hand and the reconfigurability of the folding tool to achieve various shapes of the modules on the other hand. The manufacturing precision of the CRC waterbomb modules is a key factor to assure compatibility between the modules in the assembled state. Therefore, the geometry is quantified and assessed using the data from systematically acquired 3D scans of the produced modules [9-11]. From the 3D scans, the position of the crease nodes and the parallelism between the facets are compared to the analytical CAD geometry to detect the creases and facets with geometrical deviations. Furthermore,

considering both the resource efficiency and economy of the manufacturing process, it is advantageous if a single folding tool has the flexibility to fold-in-fresh different waterbomb patterns.

The paper is structured as follows: First, a brief description of the proposed modules and the manufacturing process is given, see Section 2. This Section is followed by a short presentation of the used folding tool built in previous research in Section 3. Then in Section 4 the scan procedure of the modules is discussed with special emphasis on the post-processing and reconstruction of the scanned geometry based on the scanned point clouds. Afterwards in Section 5, a statistical analysis is carried out to quantify the deviations between the analytical and scanned geometry, and suggestions to improve the tool's accuracy are discussed in Section 6. Finally, possibilities and limitations of flexibilization concepts for the folding tool are identified and discussed.

2 Carbon-reinforced concrete waterbomb modules

The manufactured CRC waterbomb modules presented in this paper consist of two layers of carbon-reinforcement CARBOrefit-Type 1 from Carbocon GmbH embedded in a concrete matrix of TF10CARBOrefit from PAGEL, which are cast in a flat state on top of the folding tool. For a folding angle of 39° , the reinforcement exhibits minor undulations, as it is impregnated and folded while still fresh.

The flat sheet of concrete and reinforcement is folded using fold-in-fresh methodology, in which the formwork is folded to the final geometry while the concrete is still fresh [5]. The formwork replicates the folding geometry of the waterbomb pattern by means of a pneumatically driven folding tool introduced by [6]. The entire folding process is fully automated and takes about 5 seconds. The folding tool remains in a folded configuration for 24 hours to allow the concrete to harden before removal. The final shape of the manufactured module is determined by the surface of the folding tool. The geometric accuracy relative to the analytical geometry depends on how precisely the folding tool can replicate the folding kinematics. To quantify the manufacturing precision of the folding tool and identify the locations, which present geometrical deviations, scans of the manufactured modules are systematically carried out. Fig. 1 a) depicts the fabricated carbon-reinforced concrete waterbomb modules. Fig. 1 b) shows the dimensions of the waterbomb module in folded state with thickness of 15 mm. Fig. 1 c) illustrates an assembly of 11 waterbomb modules and 6 half waterbomb modules assembled and held together by topological interlocking properties. Fig. 1 d) shows the scanning process of the waterbomb module.

Fig. 1 Carbon-reinforced concrete waterbomb modules. a) Manufactured modules and half modules by "fold-in-fresh" methodology. b) Dimensions of the waterbomb module. c) CAD illustration of the assembly of waterbomb modules d) Scanning process of the bottom surface of the waterbomb module under indirect natural illumination.

[mm]

3 Presentation of the used novel folding tool

The tool used to fold the concrete elements was developed and built as a demonstrator in a preliminary study for flexible folding of textile-reinforced concrete components. To reduce complexity, this demonstrator initially dispenses the ability to shape different geometries. Nevertheless, this study already gives us detailed insights into the behavior of and interactions between the concrete, the reinforcement, the tool, and the folding process.

The surfaces of the folding tool consist of rigid facets replicating the waterbomb pattern and its crease arrangement. These facets are built as steel sheets, which are fixed on top of a continuous fiber-reinforced plastic membrane. The continuous and flexible plastic membrane acts as a seal between the facets so that the concrete in fresh state is kept within the tool's formwork. A continuous transition from a planar to a folded, complex three-dimensional state is accomplished through the translational and rotational movement of the facets in space, achieved by an appropriate mechanism beneath the tool surface. The non-fixed spaces between the facets thereby serve as revolute joints. Without further stiffening measures, however, this realization of the revolute joints leads to considerable tolerances in the folded state of the tool when actuating at just one point due to the flexibility of the membrane connection. For this reason, additional constraints were added to the tool surface by mechanically linking various facet movements using additional bearings. Here, for simplicity reasons, the symmetry to the longitudinal and transverse axes of the waterbomb modules is utilized. Despite the multiple static overdeterminations of the tool resulting from this stiffening with the bearings, no jamming occurs during actuation. The actuation of the tool itself occurs pneumatically at several points with a force that is adapted to the particular drive group and the course of movement. Fig. 2 shows the tool in the folded state as well as the dimensions of the tool surface.

Fig. 2 a) Folding tool from the preliminary study by [6]. b) Dimensions of the waterbomb pattern in flat state.

It should be noted that the center of rotation between two facets in the presented design of the revolute joints is neither within the textile reinforcement nor within the middle of the module's height, but in the plane of the membrane and therefore no ideal folding process takes place. The resulting effects on the folding process and the concrete component will be examined in the following. A detailed description of the folding tool with a special focus on the requirements for and the effects on the textile reinforcement during the folding process is presented in [6]. Furthermore, deficits of the folding tool from the preliminary study and open questions already suspected during the design of the tool are presented in that paper.

4 3D scans of the waterbomb modules

The scans of the waterbomb modules were conducted utilizing the Go!SCAN SPARK device from CREAFORM. This device is equipped with white light and cameras, which capture the geometry with a mesh resolution of 1 mm, a measurement accuracy of 0.5 mm, and a scanning velocity of 1,500,000 measurements per second tailored for our application. The manufactured waterbomb modules were placed in a position avoiding direct sunlight and reflections to prevent data distortion, as shown in Fig. 1 b).

The scans are conducted in a systematic manner on the bottom surface of each CRC waterbomb module, starting at the upper-left corner and proceeding in horizontal rows, advancing across the surface until the module is entirely scanned, always maintaining a working distance of 200-300 mm from the scanner to the measured surface, as shown in Fig. 1 d). The scan procedure was carried out for the 8 manufactured CRC waterbomb modules.

Manually analyzing the obtained geometric data by means of CAD software is not a precise and effective approach. Therefore, a Python-based analysis workflow was developed to systematically process and reconstruct the scanned geometry, based on the geometric data, and compare it to its analytical counterpart on a common coordinate system. The analysis workflow comprises four steps. The first step involves extracting point clouds for each facet, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (1), with each color representing a distinct point cloud. In the second step, a plane is fitted to each point cloud and the intersections between these planes, which correspond to the crease lines, are identified, as depicted in Fig. 3 (2). The third step involves determining intersection points (crease nodes) between these crease lines, enabling the reconstruction of scanned facets based on the connectivity of the crease nodes, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (3). Finally, the analytical and scanned geometries are aligned within a common reference frame and their deviations are quantitatively assessed. The analysis workflow is publicly available on GitHub [bmcs_shell](#) [12].

Fig. 3 Flowchart of the automated post-processing and analysis of the scanned data. The numbering depicted aims to identify the crease lines and crease nodes.

4.1 Extracting the point clouds and identifying the crease lines

To initiate the reconstruction of the scanned waterbomb geometry, a point cloud is extracted from the 3D scan data corresponding to each individual facet, resulting in a total of 14 point clouds, each illustrated in a different color, as depicted in Fig. 3 (1). Each point cloud must consist of at least three points so that a plane can be fitted to it. These point clouds were then numbered consistently with the facets, ranging from 0 to 13 in an anticlockwise direction, as illustrated in Fig. 4 a). For each point cloud, a plane was fitted using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), minimizing the total distance to the points in a least-squares sense. This process yields the plane equations, with their coefficients defining the planes' orientation and position in space.

The fitted planes span through a Cartesian three-dimensional space. Since the planes represent the facets, their intersections delineate the folding crease lines of the geometry. Each crease line is parametrized by a direction vector based on a reference point lying on the line and satisfying the equations of both intersecting planes. This parametrization enables a mathematical description of every point along the crease lines, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (2).

Fig. 4 Numbering of the facets and crease nodes of the waterbomb pattern following the convention used to reconstruct the geometry

4.2 Reconstructing the geometry

The reconstruction of the facets was carried out by identifying the crease nodes and connecting them to form a surface. The intersection of the crease lines defines the crease nodes, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (3). Once the intersection nodes were identified, their connectivity was established to form the facets based on the numbering convention defined in Fig. 4 b).

Crease nodes, like those at the boundaries, cannot all be defined by crease line intersections. The positions of the boundary crease nodes were then determined by extending the corresponding crease lines by the average length of their counterpart crease lines. For example, the positions of crease nodes 8, 11, 14, and 17 were found by extending their crease lines in the direction of the direction vector by the average length of the crease lines made by nodes (6, 4), (6, 2), (7, 3), and (7, 5).

After identifying all valley and mountain nodes, geometric consistency was enforced by adjusting the positions of the corner nodes, since the valley creases are intended to form a rectangular layout. Specifically, the x -coordinates of the valley nodes were corrected to align accurately with the corresponding mountain nodes. Following this procedure, the scanned geometry of the waterbomb modules was successfully reconstructed from the point cloud data.

4.3 Common reference coordinate system

The reconstructed geometry from the scanned point clouds aims for a direct comparison with its analytically described geometry in a systematic and precise form. To enable this comparison, both geometries need to be aligned on the same coordinate system and origin. Therefore, a local coordinate system was established, providing a shared reference frame for evaluating the geometric deviations.

The local coordinate system is described by an orthonormal basis and its unit vectors, as shown in red in Fig. 3 (4). The origin of the local coordinate system is located at the midpoint of the deepest valley crease defined between crease nodes 0 and 1 (see Fig. 4). The orientation of the local x -axis is congruent with the deepest valley's crease line, with the positive direction designated from the left crease node to the right crease node. The local x -axis was defined by averaging the normal vectors of facets 3 and 10 (adjacent to the deepest valley crease), which results in a vector pointing in the z -direction. The local y -axis was defined by the cross product of the basis vectors that describe the x - and z -directions, ensuring orthogonality. Thus, the local coordinate system is oriented by the x , y , z -axis with its origin at the deepest valley crease midpoint.

Nonetheless, manufacturing imperfections lead to slight deviation in the orientation and symmetry of the facets, potentially affecting the orthogonality of the initially computed basis vector based on facets 3 and 10. Therefore, the z -basis vector is subsequently re-calibrated using the cross product of the x - and y -basis vectors to enforce orthogonality among all three basis vectors of the local coordinate system. This procedure guarantees a consistent orthogonal local coordinate system that facilitates an accurate comparison between the analytically determined and the scanned geometry.

Furthermore, the coordinates of the node creases from both analytical and scanned geometries are transformed into the local coordinate system. The transformation is accomplished by a change of basis,

whereby the crease nodes are projected onto the local coordinate system. This process facilitates a direct comparison of the crease nodes' position within the local system. Additionally, the crease length and the normal vector to the facets serve as evaluation criteria for the folding precision.

4.4 Statistical evaluation of the manufacturing imperfections

This section presents a statistical analysis of the geometric deviations between the analytical and scanned geometries of the 8 manufactured waterbomb modules. The aim is to identify statistically significant deviations, highlighting areas where improvements in the folding tool are needed to achieve a more precise manufacturing of the waterbomb modules. The analysis focuses on two key aspects: the positions of the 18 crease nodes and the angle formed by normal vectors of the 14 facets of the scanned and analytical geometry.

The angle between the normal vectors of the analytical and scanned facets provides a key measure of manufacturing precision, as it reflects the overall facet orientation and the impact of its constituent nodes on the geometrical imperfections. Facet parallelism is essential for proper engagement of the facets of adjacent waterbomb modules in a topological interlocking assembled condition. Misaligned facets induce localized bending generated by the action of dead and live loads, leading to unforeseen stress distribution and failure modes in the assembled state. Fig. 5 a) shows the average angle formed between normal vectors among the eight analyzed modules. Facets 0, 2, 3, 5, 6, and 10 exhibit the smallest average angular deviations. The facets 1, 4, 7, 8, 9, and 11 show an average angular deviation between 1 and 3 degrees, indicating a moderate deviation. The facets 1, 4, 7, 8, 9, 11 show an average angular deviation between 1 and 3 degrees, indicating a moderate deviation. Facet 12 shows the largest average angular deviation of 3.62 ± 0.57 degrees.

Further, the deviation in the positions of the 18 crease nodes were examined. Fig. 5 b) shows the average crease node deviations among the 8 scanned modules. Each bar represents the mean Euclidean distance between the analytical and scanned crease nodes and the error bars represent the standard deviations of these distances. The results indicate that the largest mean deviations are observed for nodes 13 and 17, 13.72 ± 1.76 mm and 13.69 ± 1.37 mm, respectively, while the smallest deviations occur in the central nodes 0 and 1, located near the origin of the local coordinate system. The nodes 2, 3, 4, and 5 forming the lower and upper facets adjacent to the deepest valley exhibit the medium deviations between 6 and 8 mm. This indicates a higher susceptibility of the outer crease nodes to deviate from the analytical geometry during the folding process. This is to be expected, as the inner crease line is used as a geometric reference for the measurement.

The current deviations in the geometry of the tool surface were already predicted in [6] and have now been confirmed by 3D measurements. Fig. 5 clearly shows that the standard deviation is low for most angles and points. This proves that the folding process is fundamentally robust and reproducible, as systematic errors dominate over stochastic errors. These systematic deviations are particularly caused by the mechanical structure of the folding tool but only enabled by the design of the folding joints. The mechanics below the tool facets reveal coarse tolerances caused by inaccuracies in the manufacturing of the folding tool. The reason for this does not lie in the components themselves, but in the insufficiently accurate assembly of certain drive and guiding components.

Fig. 5 a) Statistical analysis of the mean Euclidean distance and its standard deviation between the crease nodes of the analytical and scanned geometries b) Statistical evaluation of the mean angle formed between the normal of the analytical and scanned facets.

The prismatic joints of facets 3 and 10 are mounted coaxially to each other and parallel to the y -axis, see Fig. 4 a). As a result, the mean deviation of the angles from ideal geometry is small. The parallel guide of facets 0 and 6 is mounted parallel to the x -axis, which results in small mean deviations of these facets from the analytical geometry. On the other hand, the parallel guide of the opposite facets 7 and 13 is mounted imprecisely, causing the normal vectors of these facets to deviate more from ideal geometry. This one-sided non-parallel positioning to the x -axis of the guiding mechanism in the tool frame is only possible because of the elastic joint design exploiting the flexibility of the membrane. Vice versa, the non-actuated facets are forced into positions that deviate from the analytical geometry. The elastic joint design prevents the gear from jamming.

By connecting a facet with a small mean deviation with a facet with a higher mean deviation, a deviation from the scanned facets compared to the analytical facets is unavoidable. Non-actuated facets 8 and 9 as well as non-actuated facets 11 and 12 are examples of this. The mean deviations as well as the standard deviations of these facets are significantly higher. On the one hand, this indicates that the kinematics of the drive have not been realized with sufficient precision, forcing the non-actuated facets into positions that deviate from ideal by squeezing the folding joints, as otherwise a continuous transition between the deviations would be expected. On the other hand, this shows that the current joint design does not guarantee exact reproducibility of the facet position when the facets are not directly actuated.

The deviations of the crease nodes directly result from the angular deviation of the facets. As the distance to the coordinate origin and the angular deviation of the facets directly determine the amount of deviation of the crease nodes from the analytical counterparts, the boundary points of the waterbomb module show the highest mean deviations. In addition, when considering the deviations of the crease nodes, it once again becomes obvious that the parallel guide of the tool was not mounted symmetrically. For example, crease node 13 shows a higher mean deviation than its mirror-symmetrical crease node 16.

5 Flexibilization concepts of the folding tool

The flexible use of a single folding tool, i.e. the ability to reconfigure the facets to form different waterbomb patterns with the same folding tool, ensures an automated and economical production of those modules. This approach represents a key difference to the initial demonstrator used in this paper. Consequently, it is necessary to develop a general flexibilization concept of the folding tool besides resolving the deficits at component level, revealed by the 3D measurements of the waterbomb modules in this paper. The degree of flexibilization that can be achieved by the folding tool depends largely on the design of the tool surface and the (multi-)actuator system below the facets. Accordingly, a trade-off between the degree of flexibilization and the correlating system complexity must be found during the development phase.

Flexibilization of the tool surface is made possible by integrating fold lines for various modules to be formed into the same tool surface. The surface of the folding tool is therefore built up from many micro facets, which when combined create the macro facets required for module-specific folding as shown in Fig. 6. Consequently, not all folding lines are ever used simultaneously.

Fig. 6 Flexibilization concept of the tool surface using tessellation into micro facets then creating macro facets

For proper performance of the tool surface, the micro facets must be stiffened to form the macro facets. Looking at the current folding tool, Fig. 2, inserting pneumatic cylinders for the individual actuation of every micro facet is the most straightforward way of implementing this necessary stiffness of the micro facets. In this concept, each micro facet is equipped with at least one pneumatic cylinder, which is fixed both in the tool frame and to the micro facet by a spherical joint. The cylinders are controlled in such a way that the micro facets of a macro facet currently in use move planar guaranteeing a perfect formwork that replicates the chosen waterbomb tessellation. In addition, a further punctual fixation of the system, e.g. in the center of the membrane sheet, is necessary so that the overall system is sufficiently kinematically determined. The exact positioning and the actual number of cylinders required are determined by the resulting kinematic relationships.

However, the low development effort in terms of hardware for the concept of actuating every micro facet by at least one pneumatic cylinder is offset by a very high level in terms of control technology. Perfect synchronization of the movement of the micro facets must be guaranteed for the functional implementation of this concept. Due to the low system stiffness resulting from the use of a highly compressible fluid inside the cylinders and joint tolerances between the micro facets, significant tolerance variations can be expected during the operation of the tool given the non-trivial motion task. In addition, there is the risk of simply damaging the membrane due to the large number of sharp angles in the micro tessellated tool surface, which only represent no potential for damaging the membrane if the actuation is executed perfectly. Moreover, this complex multi-actuator system is to be assessed negatively from an economic point of view, since, when supplied by a constant pressure system, a dedicated (proportional) valve is required for every actuator on top of the large number of cylinders itself. Further, it should be noted that the degree of flexibility and reconfigurability of this concept is limited by the knowledge of all folding patterns at the initial stage of development. The extension by new folding lines goes hand in hand with the redesign and new production of the tool surface.

The folding tool's control performance can be improved by reducing the number of pneumatic cylinders. Limiting the number of actuators to the fold-specific minimum is only possible if the cylinders can be positioned anywhere in the tool frame, i.e. individually for each tool configuration specified by the waterbomb geometry. Accordingly, the attachment of the cylinders in the tool frame and to the facets must be designed removable. Adding or removing actuators also needs to be possible without any problems. Further research into possible realization concepts of this attachment is required to ensure a folding tool that is both flexible and easy to handle.

One concept, for instance, is to include a large number of ports for compressed air in the tool frame, which at the same time serve as mechanical coupling between the cylinders and the tool frame. The actuators can be positioned manually or automatically, using existing handling systems for simple positioning tasks. Decentralized electrical power supply, control and signal processing of the actuators, i.e. directly at the cylinders themselves, e.g. using a switching valve with a sufficiently small flow rate and a battery-powered microcontroller with WiFi, further improve and simplify this concept. A schematic illustration of this concept is shown in Fig. 7. This concept significantly increases the degree of flexibility and reconfigurability on behalf of the actuators and serves as basis for the tool surface concepts presented hereafter.

Fig. 7 Flexibilization concept of the tool drive using minimum number of cylinders with decentralized electrical power supply, control and signal processing as well as spherical, position-variable joints with ports for compressed air

Reducing the number of cylinders to the module-specific minimum requires efforts at reducing the degrees of freedom of the tool surface. The tessellation of the surface into micro facets described above is no longer possible unless the micro facets can be stiffened to the macro facets using additional, e.g. pneumatically actuated, mechanisms located directly beneath the tool surface. By this mechanical stiffening of the micro facets a significantly higher accuracy of the folding tool is ensured compared to the accuracy achievable by cylinder controlled micro facets. This is because the number of joints is reduced to a minimum and planar macro facets can be guaranteed by the stiffening of all folding lines that are not in use. However, in addition to the high costs that may arise depending on the design of the stiffening mechanisms, there is still the concept-related necessity that all positions of the fold lines need to be known when designing the tool surface. As an intermediate concept, the use of several module-specific tool surfaces therefore is a reasonable solution. This also offers the advantage of easily integrating new folding patterns into the tool by simply creating new tool surfaces.

Providing maximum flexibility and reconfigurability to the tool surface with maximum stiffness at the same time is achieved by individually equipping the folding tool with module-specific macro facets. Therefore, each waterbomb geometry requires a specific set of facets that does not cover the folding lines currently being used but stiffens the rest of the membrane on both the top and bottom sides at the same positions. One concept of fixing the facets to the membrane is using strong permanent magnets integrated into the facets to clamp the membrane between them. Depending on the degree of automation of the overall system, the placing process, which must be carried out simultaneously from above and below when using magnetic connectors, can be carried out manually or with the help of two robots or other positioning systems with at least three axes. This concept additionally requires the ability to lock the membrane in the tool frame while changing the facets. A draft of this concept is shown in Fig. 8. Besides the highest possible stiffness of the tool surface, the easy replacement of all components is a major advantage. The reusability of individual facets for different waterbomb modules must be investigated. Adding new folding patterns is no difficulty as well. On the other hand, costs may be higher due to the required positioning systems needed for attaching the facets to the membrane. The previously mentioned trade-off between the degree of flexibility and the system complexity must be considered in this context. Combinations of different concepts also seem conceivable.

Fig. 8 Overall concept for the flexibilization of the folding tool using module-specific assembly of the tool surface by robots and position-variable actuators as drive

6 Conclusion and outlook

Flexibility and precision in the manufacturing process of carbon-reinforced concrete waterbomb modules are essential for the design of modular structural systems. While the flexibility of the manufacturing tool provides the freedom to design CRC waterbomb modules tailored for a specific purpose, the precision of the process guarantees the compatibility and integrity of these modules in assembled state. Casting carbon-reinforced concrete waterbomb modules using the “fold-in-fresh” methodology by means of an innovative and automated, pneumatically actuated folding tool is an approach to guarantee both precision and efficiency.

The surface of the folding tool consists of numerous rigid steel facets that are linked by a flexible, fiber-reinforced plastic membrane replicating the waterbomb pattern. Thus, the membrane serves both as a revolute joint and as a seal between the facets. Nevertheless, the statistical analysis of 3D scan data from this study shows that neither the precision in manufacturing the tool nor the joint design at this point guarantee a precise geometrical reproduction of waterbomb modules compared to its analytical counterpart.

Furthermore, flexibilization concepts were presented enabling future production of modules with different geometries using the same folding tool. In this context, it was shown to be beneficial to implement position-independent actuators with decentralized power supply, control, and signal processing. The highest flexibility is ensured by a tool surface, which is individually equipped with matching facets.

Future work will focus on developing a suitable joint design for the tool surface with special focus on the optimal center of rotation to improve the tool’s precision and CRC module quality. Optical geometry feedback of the component during the folding process and individual pneumatic control of the facets are expected to further improve manufacturing precision. For these investigations, a test rig with a limited number of facets will be set up during the project to allow simple testing and validation of new concepts. At the same time, the design of the flexibilization concepts will be continued. Besides this, there will also be studies on the drapability of the textile and the tessellation of the tool surface.

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